

LITERARY PSEUDONYMS ON THE EXAMPLE OF RUSSIAN AND UZBEK WRITERS

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Abstract. *Research into the reasons for the appearance of pseudonyms of famous writers and poets, their classification according to methods of education; finding out the reasons why famous personalities abandon their real names and take pseudonyms. Find out how relevant the use of pseudonyms is in modern times.. Despite the fact that there are monographs, dictionaries and encyclopedias on pseudonyms, pseudonyms - a large layer of unofficial names - have not yet been sufficiently studied from the point of view of linguistic theory, so they are of particular linguistic interest.*

Getting to know fictitious names will deepen the knowledge of philology students in the field of anthroponymy, help expand their horizons and develop anthroponymic skills and linguistic competence in general.

Keywords: *anthroponym, pseudonyms, fictitious names, linguoculturology.*

Most fictitious names contain a semantic component, so it should be noted that their semantics, unlike real names, is “speaking” (for example, M. Gorky, D. Bedny, Sasha Cherny, Andrey Bely, etc.). Thus, perhaps the most important literary pseudonym in Russia of the 20th century is Maxim Gorky, which belonged to Alexei Maksimovich Peshkov (1868–1936). Most commonly used words have multiple meanings, and the word “gorky” is no exception in this regard. The Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language notes the following meanings:

1. Having a peculiar acrid and unpleasant taste. Bitters.
2. Sorrowful, heavy. Bitter share [11, p. 140–141].

It is easy to note that when choosing a pseudonym, the writer relied on the second meaning of the lexeme. In Russian, this adjective is very often used in phrases such as bitter share, bitter fate, bitter fate.

From the point of view of semantics, the pseudonym of the Russian prose writer, poet, journalist, satirist Alexander Mikhailovich Glikberg - Sasha Cherny - is of interest. There were five children in a large Jewish family, two of whom were Sasha. The light one was called white, and the dark one was called black. In this context, the adjective black (and therefore a pseudonym) has a direct meaning:

1. Colors of soot, coal. Black eyes.
2. Dark, as opposed to something lighter called white. Black mushroom" [11, p. 884].

At the same time, the pseudonym Cherny reflects the life of the writer and corresponds to the figurative meaning of the word presented in the dictionary: “Gloomy, joyless, heavy. Dark days” [11, p. 884].

The antonymous adjective white became the pseudonym of the Russian poet, writer, critic, memoirist Andrei Bely (real name - B. N. Bugaev). White is “light, as opposed to something darker called black. White bread” [11, p. 43]. This pseudonym was proposed to the writer by his teacher and mentor M. S. Solovyov not by chance: the white color symbolizes purity, height of thoughts

and tranquility. Apparently, M. S. Solovyov, using a pseudonym, wanted to “give” his student a bright destiny.

For example, the name Demyan Bedny is socially colored - the pseudonym of the famous Russian writer E. A. Pridvorov (1883–1945). In the surname Pridvorov one can see a double motivation, since the words “yard 1” - “yard 2” are lexical homonyms. The noun "yard" is ambiguous. Some of its meanings: 1. A plot of land between house buildings of one property, one city lot. Children's playground in the yard. 2. A peasant house with all outbuildings, a separate peasant farm. A village of one hundred yards [11, p. 154]. The homonym word “yard 2” has the meaning: “In monarchical countries: the monarch, his family and persons close to them. Imperial Courtyard. To be at court" [11, p. 154].

Since the surname Pridvorov (one should pay attention to the form of the anthroponym Pridvorov, not Pridvornov, which, nevertheless, can be associated with the word courtier - close to the court) and the peasant name Efim were not suitable for a writer of socialist realism, a member of the Communist Party, the author As a pseudonym, I chose a name used among peasants - Demyan. The surname Bedny goes back to the name of the literary hero, whom the poet himself invented in the poem “About Demyan Bedny, a harmful man.”

The pseudonym turned out to be successful: it was not only remembered immediately, but also evoked the right associations [12]. Social connotations are also characteristic of many other fictitious names.

After considering pseudonyms from the point of view of semantics, attention is paid to the paradigmatic relations of onyms. Analyzing the semantic connections of pseudonyms among fictitious names, the following can be distinguished:

a) antonym pseudonyms: Sasha Cherny (A. M. Glikberg) - Andrey Bely (B. N. Bugaev); Northerner (I.V. Lotarev) – Southerner (B.S. Gurevich);

b) synonymous pseudonyms: Bedny (E. A. Pridvorov) – Hungry (M. S. Epstein) – Pribludny (Ya. P. Ovcharenko) Bedny, Bely), and borrowed (for example, foreign language pseudonyms of A. P. Chekhov: Ulysses, Laertes, Ruver and Revur). Thanks to pseudonyms, double surnames of writers appeared. For example, the semantics of the surname Saltykov-Shchedrin is of interest. The writer's real name is Saltykov. The adjective generous, according to the Explanatory Dictionary of the Russian Language, has multiple meanings:

1. Willing to spend on others, not stingy. Generous relative.
2. Valuable, rich. Generous gifts.
3. Transfer. Abundant, frequent. Generous rains [11, p. 903]. According to one version, M. E. Saltykov’s wife suggested taking such a pseudonym, since in his works he was very generous “with all kinds of sarcasm”

Results

As a result of working on fictitious names, one can be convinced that there are quite a lot of reasons for the appearance and methods of forming pseudonyms of writers. “Acquaintance with them, their “decoding” are of particular interest from both a linguistic and linguocultural point of view. Studying the nature of pseudonyms not only broadens students’ horizons, but also allows them to penetrate into the laboratory of an artist of words, revealing his creative potential and moral positions.” An unusual name has always been a kind of marker. It distinguished a person from the crowd, pointed to his dissimilarity (appearance), special pedigree, distinctive skills.

Sometimes the name became a heavy burden. After all, you had to meet the expectations of society, to be the same as, for example, your talented ancestor.

A classification table of methods for forming pseudonyms was compiled. For analysis, the pseudonyms of eight famous writers and poets of the 19th and 20th centuries were chosen.

Author's real name	Nickname	Formation of a nickname
Anton Pavlovich Chekhov	Antosha Chekhonte	A derivative of a surname, a diminutive name. Chekhonte is a word consisting of two words CHEKHOV + anTon = CHEKHONTE This nickname was given to young Anton by the teacher of the Taganrog gymnasium Fyodor Pokrovsky
Alexey Maksimovich Peshkov	Maksim Gorky	Pseudonym-phrenonym: it characterizes not only his fate, but also the direction of his work. Derived from the adjective sorrowful, heavy. Bitter share
Efim Alekseevich Pridvorov	Demyan Bedny	Demian is a male Russian personal name. According to one version, it supposedly goes back to lat. Damianus - "dedicated to Damia", in Greek mythology - the locally revered goddess of fertility and abundance. "Poor" he took the village nickname of his uncle,
Alexey Konstantinovich Tolstoy	Kozma Prutkov	Creation of a collective pseudonym (literary mask)
Ivan Sergeevich Turgenev	T. L. (Turgenev-Lutovinov)	Combination of one's own surname and mother's surname (Lutovinova, family estate Spasskoye-Lutovinovo)
Mikhail Afanasyevich Bulgakov	Mikhail Bull	Dropping the end of a surname
Mikhail Evgrafovich Saltykov	Saltykov - Shchedrin.	From the adjective generous, Shchedrin chose the pseudonym on the advice of his wife as a derivative of the word 'generous', since in his writings he was extremely generous with all kinds of sarcasm.

Anna Andreevna Gorenko	Anna Akhmatova	turned to the family tree of the family. The grandmother of the future poetess believed that her family descended from the famous Horde Khan Akhmat.

The main reasons why people use pseudonyms are:

-In the 19th century, these were, first of all, censorship, the first literary experience and class prejudices.

- fear of persecution, test of pen, cacophony of first or last name.
- the influence of social status, another profession, first literary experience.

For satirists and humorists at all times - to produce a comic effect.

Through the definition of classification, we learned what an amazing variety of nicknames there is in a world that we had no idea about.

There are cases when works are not signed, are passed off as finds or translations, or are attributed to another person, but more often, in order to hide authorship, they resort to a pseudonym.

The most inventive writers of Russian and Uzbek literature of the 19th century in inventing pseudonyms were Anton Pavlovich Chekhov and Abdullah Kodiriy. Both writers had a wonderful sense of humor and created their pseudonyms not in order to hide their own authorship, but in order to amuse the reader and intrigue him

Comparison table “absolute record holders in this area”

Russian writer of the 19th century	Uzbek writer of the 19th century
<p>Abdullah Kodiriy</p> <p>Nicknames:</p> <p>Zhulkunboy, Zhirkinboy, Zh-boy, Zhu-boy, U-boy, F, Zhulkunboy Sov-rinboy ugli, Mulla Zhulkunboy, Zhulkinchitir, Dumbulboy, Zhulbulboy zhiyani, Dumbulboy ugli, Dumbul Devon, Dumbulnisa, Domladumbul, Zhiyan, Zhiyaningiz Mushtum , Kalvak makhzum, Kalvak makhzum zhiyani, Kalvak makhzum Shoshiy, Toshpulat, Toshpulat tazhang, Alimov, A.K, Boykush, Indamas sufi, Yulovchi, Kampir, Karnaiichi, Kolkhozchi, Gaznitchi, Lakalang mazum, Mavlon kufur, Mushtum, Sani hudo, Te forehead .</p>	

A. Pavlov, Panko, Colonel Kochkarev, Prose poet, Ruver, Ruver and Revur, Ulysses, Ts., Ch., Ch. B.S.Ch. without s., Person. b. spleen., Man without a spleen, Chekhonte, Ch. Khonte, A., Tsyntsynnatus, Champagne, Schiller, Shakespeareovich Goethe.	
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The process of forming pseudonyms is a continuous search for a convenient form that meets the needs of people to identify their personality, corresponding to traditions, customs, unique fashion and time. The study of proper names is always relevant, especially in connection with the continuity and evolutionary nature of the development of society, in which names play the role of a kind of mirror, reflecting the history and culture of the people. The results obtained can be used in classes on linguistic and regional studies, theory and practice of translation, intercultural communication

Discussion

There is a Latin proverb: “Habent sua fata libelli” - “Every book has its own destiny.” We can say that each pseudonym has its own destiny. Often his life was short: the fictitious name under which the aspiring author, out of caution or for other reasons, entered the literary field turned out to be unnecessary and was discarded. But sometimes, and not so rarely, a literary surname completely replaced the real one, both on the pages of books and in the lives of their authors.

Pseudonyms deserve study as one of the important factors in the literary life of all times and peoples. We think that getting to know such an interesting topic will broaden the horizons of literature lovers.

The name has a greater impact on the life and character of its bearer. And when adopting false names, a certain personality is formed, associated with the combination of last name, first name and patronymic. That is, it turns out that by choosing a pseudonym, the writer himself chooses his own destiny, first of all, in writing. For some, changing their name will bring success and fame, for others, on the contrary, it will be a fatal step in their career.

Hearing a person's nickname, we learn much more about him than hearing just his name. After all, a pseudonym characterizes a person and carries a large flow of information about him. It was very interesting for us to conduct this research; it makes us want to look into the mystery of the name, to understand the reasons that prompt people to take this or that pseudonym.

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